

THE STUDY OF METHYL METHACRYLATE HARDENED HYBRID POPLAR WOOD

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Abstract

Wood of fast-growing hybrid poplars (*Populus × euramericana*), consisting of six 6-year-old clones in one plantation in Quebec, was impregnated with methyl methacrylate (MMA) and then polymerized by heat/catalyst method. The physical and mechanical properties of the poplar clones and their MMA-hardened wood related to potential end uses were investigated. The effects of MMA hardening on the density, volume swelling coefficient (S), surface properties (hardness and abrasion resistance) and mechanical properties (flexural and compressive strength) were studied. Scanning electron microscopy and fourier transform infrared analysis showed that filling the voids in the wood structure was the main hardening mechanism. The incorporation of the polymer increased the density of all of the poplar clones by 120–160% and decreased the water migration rate into the wood during the soaking. S values of hardened woods were significantly lower than those of controls, depending on the clone type. Incorporating MMA effectively improved the dimensional stability of poplar wood at the early soaking stage, but was less effective in the long term. The Janka hardness was found to be 2.5–4 times higher in the treated poplar wood than in the untreated poplar wood. The treated wood also exhibited superior abrasion resistance. Significant differences were observed among clones in bending and compression strength parallel to grain. Hardening treatment has considerably improved all strength properties except for strain at rupture in static bending. The improved properties of MMA-hardened hybrid poplar were comparable to some commercial hardwood species.

1 Introduction

Wood is a natural and renewable material. It has been used for construction, tools, furniture, and artistic medium for thousands of years due to its high strength-to-weight ratio, unique porous structure, and aesthetic characteristics. However, faced with dwindling supply of high-quality lumber from natural forestry and stricter environmental regulations, poplar (*Populus spp.*) and its hybrids have been considered as alternative wood source due to their rapid growth and ease of reproduction [1, 2]. It represents one of the most widespread broad-leaved species in North America [3]. It is estimated that poplars account for over 50% of all hardwoods and approximately 11% of the entire Canadian timber resource [4]. According to a recent report [5], harvested poplar wood in Quebec was 2,164,000 m³ in 2009, which was almost 45 % of the total hardwood production. Nevertheless, it has long been characterized as a low-density (specific gravity: 0.30-0.39), low-strength wood species [3, 6]. Standing poplar trees have high moisture content, typically almost 100%, with only minor differences between sapwood and heartwood [3]. Poplar wood is bright and light in color, with a straight grain and uniform texture [7]. Its low extractive content makes it liable to discoloration and decay [3]. Currently, poplar wood is primarily servicing as fiber for pulp and paper industry, and as engineered wood products such as oriented strand board, laminated veneer lumber and structural composite lumber [3].

To improve the physical and mechanical properties of poplar wood, modification of its porous structure is regarded as an effective way. Wood hardening, which is a method of impregnating chemicals into

wood pores and subsequently curing the chemicals by radiation or catalyst-thermal treatment, has received considerable attention. After wood hardening, not only the strength, but also the density, surface and thermal properties, dimensional stability, and durability of the poplar wood are enhanced [8-19]. Different polymeric monomers and resins have been employed, including methyl methacrylate [8, 10, 11, 14, 15, 17, 19], styrene [15, 16, 19], polyurethane resin [13], and maleic anhydride [17, 18]. Among those chemicals, methyl methacrylate is the most commonly used due to its cheap price, accessibility and low viscosity [20, 21].

So far, very few studies on physical and mechanical properties of MMA hardened poplar wood have been carried out and the properties were not studied systematically [14, 18, 19]. Information on these properties is lacking for not only hardened wood but for wood in general. This property determines the suitability of the wood for various high value applications, such as flooring, furniture table tops, and other uses, where the wood is subject to various environmental conditions, load, and traffic and mechanical friction and abrasion. Thus, the objectives of this study were (1) to understand the interaction between the hybrid poplar wood structure and the MMA monomer, (2) to evaluate the effect of MMA hardening on the density, dimensional stability, surface properties, and mechanical properties of hybrid poplar wood, (3) to study the interclonal variations in the density, dimensional stability, surface properties, and mechanical properties of hardened and nonhardened wood, and (4) to investigate the potential of impregnated hybrid poplar wood for high-value products.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Twenty-four hybrid poplar trees were chosen randomly from a six-year-old experimental plantation near Montreal, Quebec, Canada (Table 1). From each tree, a log was taken at between 0.5 m and breast height, and samples were extracted to measure the physical and mechanical properties. From each log, four standard specimens were prepared for each investigated property, according to standard test methods, to evaluate wood density, dimensional stability, hardness, abrasion resistance, three-point static bending, and compressive strength

(both parallel and perpendicular to grain). The four specimens from each tree for each test were divided into two equally sized groups: a control group and a treated group. The controls were kept in an air-conditioned room at 21 °C and 40 % relative humidity for 60 days to reach a moisture content of 9% before testing. The treated group was designated for the hardening treatment.

Table 1 General information on hybrid poplar clones

Clone	Clone code	Species cross	No. of trees
1	915313	<i>P.maximowiczii</i> × <i>deltooides</i>	4
2	915508	<i>P.maximowiczii</i> × <i>deltooides</i>	4
3	3729	<i>P.nigra</i> × <i>maximowiczii</i>	4
4	915303	<i>P.maximowiczii</i> × <i>deltooides</i>	4
5	915311	<i>P.maximowiczii</i> × <i>deltooides</i>	4
6	3531	<i>P.deltooides</i> × <i>nigra</i>	4

An impregnating solution was formulated from a hydroquinone-inhibited monomer (methyl methacrylate MMA, $H_2C=C(CH_3)COOCH_3$), provided by Univar Canada Ltd. (Richmond, British Columbia, Canada), mixed with 0.5 wt.% of Vazo 52 (2,2'-azobis-2,4-dimethylvaleronitrile), a low temperature polymerization initiator obtained from DuPont Canada Inc. (Mississauga, Ontario, Canada). The 0.5 wt % of Vazo 52 was based on the weight of the polymeric monomer mixture. The monomer solution was prepared immediately before the impregnation process to prevent self-assembling into polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) polymer.

2.2 Hardening process

Wood specimens were preconditioned at 9 % moisture content (MC). The samples were then placed in an autoclave where a vacuum of 10 kPa was applied for 20 minutes before pouring the impregnation solution, followed by a pressure up to 1.38 MPa for 20 minutes. The impregnated samples were then polymerized at 70 °C under N_2 pressure and a pressure of 690 kPa for 4 hours.

2.3 Characterization

Polymer retention (PR) in the composites was calculated according to equation 1:

$$PR (\%) = (w_{hw} - w_s) / w_s \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where w_{hw} is the weight of the hardened wood sample and w_s is the initial weight of the corresponding untreated sample.

Samples with nominal dimensions $100 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$ (longitudinal \times radial \times tangential, $L \times R \times T$) were used to determine oven-dried density (ρ_o). The samples were oven-dried for more than 24 hours at $103 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to achieve a constant weight. The dimensions of the samples were then determined in the three principal directions to the nearest 0.01 mm and weight was recorded to the nearest 0.01 g. ρ_o was calculated according to equation 2:

$$\rho_o = M_o / V_o \quad (2)$$

where M_o and V_o are the mass and volume of the oven-dried sample, respectively.

Density profiles of the hardened and nonhardened wood samples were measured with an X-ray densitometer on samples 2.5 cm in width. In order to observe the microstructure, the samples were fractured in a brittle manner after immersing them into liquid nitrogen. The fractured surface was coated with a thin layer of platinum using a sputter coater (SC7620, Quorum Technologies, West Sussex, UK), and the microstructure was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JSM-6060, JEOL, Tokyo, Japan).

The infrared spectra of the untreated hybrid poplar wood, MMA-hardened poplar wood, and PMMA samples were recorded on a Tensor 27 Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) system (Bruker Optics, Ettlingen, Germany) equipped with a deuterated triglycine sulfate detector. For each sample, spectra were recorded by the collection of 164 scans in the range $4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 4-cm^{-1} resolution. Pure powdered potassium bromide (KBr) was used as a reference substance. Samples for FTIR were carefully prepared in microcups as follows: 1 mg of each wood flour (100 mesh) or PMMA was mixed with KBr in the proportion of 1/100 wt % in an agate mortar and then transferred to a cup 4 mm in diameter, where it was lightly compressed and leveled with a spatula. Tilted baselines of the original spectra were not altered.

Samples with dimensions $100 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$ ($L \times R \times T$) were used to determine the volumetric swelling

properties according to ASTM D 1037-99. Swelling after submersion in water for periods of 2, 24, 48, 168, 336, and 720 hours were measured. After each saturation period, dimensions were determined to the nearest 0.01 mm in the three principal directions. Samples were then oven-dried for more than 24 hours at $103 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until constant weight was reached. The same measurements were then repeated on the oven-dried samples. Volumetric swelling coefficient (S) was calculated according to the equation 3:

$$S (\%) = (V_w - V_o) / V_o \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where V_o is the volume of the oven-dried sample, and V_w is the volume after water submersion.

Hardness tests were performed on a wide surface measuring $75 \times 150 \text{ mm}^2$ ($T \times L$) according to ASTM D 143-94 and with a Zwick/Roell Z020 universal testing machine (Ulm, Germany). Five penetrations were made into each specimen, with penetration points set 30 mm apart to prevent interference between the penetrations points. The specimen hardness was recorded as the average of the five hardness values measured.

The abrasion resistance was determined with a CS-17 Taber Abrader (North Tonawanda, New York, USA) according to ASTM D 4060 and was expressed as wear index, which is the weight loss in milligrams per specified number of cycles under a specified load (1000 g). The sample dimensions were $100 \times 100 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$ ($L \times R \times T$), and the weight losses after 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, and 2500 cycles were recorded. The weight was measured with a digital scale to 0.0001 g of precision. Both the control and MMA-treated composites were tested without further finishing processes.

Three-point static bending tests were carried out using a universal testing machine (Zwick/Roell Z020) with a maximum load of 20 kN. The nominal poplar wood sample size for the test is $410 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$ ($L \times R \times T$), with actual height and width at the center measured before the test. Span length was 300 mm. The remaining procedures were conducted according to ASTM D 143-94. Modulus of elasticity (MOE, MPa), modulus of rupture (MOR, MPa), proportional limit (PL, MPa), and strain at MOR (S, %) were recorded for both untreated and hardened samples.

Compression tests, parallel and perpendicular, were performed on an MTS machine with a maximum load of 50 kN. Specimens were machined to $100 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$ (L×R×T) and $50 \times 20 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$ (L×R×T) for parallel and perpendicular to grain tests, respectively. Actual cross-section area was measured before testing. Both operations were conducted in accordance with ASTM D 143-99. MOE (MPa), maximum crushing strength (MCS, MPa), and proportional limit (PL, MPa) were recorded by a computer linked to the machine for the parallel and perpendicular tests, respectively, for untreated and hardened samples.

Statistical analyses of the data were performed using Statistical Analysis System (SAS) software package [22]. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using the Proc Mixed model and Least Squares Means (LSMEANS) / P-values for differences (PDIF) option on the combined data (control and treated) to determine differences between mean values of control and treated samples in hybrid crosses. The residual normal distribution for each trait was verified by both the Shapiro–Wilk’s W test and a normal probability plot using SAS Plot and univariate procedures. The homogeneity of variance for each trait was verified graphically by scatterplots of studentized residuals versus predicted values.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Density

The hardening treatment increased the density of hybrid poplar wood by 2.2–2.6 times, to 687–805 kg/m^3 , depending on the clone. The highest value was observed for clone 3531 and the lowest for clone 915303. The density of hardened wood was similar to or higher than that of many commercial hardwood species, e.g. silver maple (667 kg/m^3), red oak (665 kg/m^3), and white ash (719 kg/m^3). Fig. 1 illustrates an example of the density profile of a hybrid poplar sample before and after hardening. This profile shows that the wood sample was impregnated through its thickness. The density of the hardened sample was much higher than that of the nonhardened wood sample. The final density of the treated wood varied with polymer retention (PR), which varied among clones. PR decreased with increasing initial wood density in the hybrid poplar clones ($R^2=0.83$). PR variation was attributed to the individual porosity of each wood [9].

Fig. 1. Density profile of hybrid poplar wood (a) and hardened hybrid poplar wood (b).

3.2 Microstructure and FTIR analysis

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs of the treated hybrid poplar wood (Fig. 2) clearly show that polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) polymer filled the vessels, lumen, and other void spaces in the wood structure.

Interaction between wood and MMA was confirmed by FTIR spectrum analysis of the untreated hybrid poplar wood, hardened wood, and PMMA, as shown in Fig. 3. The FTIR spectra for untreated samples show intensity bands in the regions 3400 cm^{-1} , 1735 cm^{-1} , 2905 cm^{-1} , 1510 and 1605 cm^{-1} , and 1158 cm^{-1} due to O–H stretching vibration, C=O stretching vibration, C–H stretching vibration, C=C stretching vibration, and C–O–C stretching vibration, respectively [18]. These absorbance bands are due to hydroxyl groups in the cellulose, a carbonyl group of acetyl ester in the hemicellulose, and carbonyl aldehyde and aromatic compounds in the lignin. The absorbance bands of PMMA at 3440 cm^{-1} , 2978 and 2878 cm^{-1} , 1731 cm^{-1} , and 1000 – 1260 cm^{-1} can be associated with –OH stretching of the lattice water, asymmetrical and symmetrical C–H stretching of CH_3 , C=O stretching, and C–O stretching, respectively [23]. The FTIR spectra of treated hybrid poplar show almost the same functional peaks as the untreated wood, but with much lower absorbance. This is probably attributable to the lower concentration of wood fibers in the reference matrix (KBr). However, the presence of an absorbance peak at around 1730 cm^{-1} may result from the formation of C=O bonds between the wood fibers and the

MMA monomer [24, 25]. However, wood lignin also contains C=O bonds. The shift of the –OH peak from 3425 cm⁻¹ in solid wood to 3445 cm⁻¹ in hardened wood was possibly due to the reaction between the –OH of the fiber cell wall and MMA [24, 26]. Change in intensity of the C–H stretching of CH₃ was also reported due to the reaction between the –OH of the wood fiber at the surface and MMA [24].

Fig.2. Scanning electron micrographs of a) Untreated and b) PMMA hardened hybrid poplar wood. Arrows indicate 1) absence of attachment of PMMA to wood tissue, and 2) unfilled cells.

3.3 Dimensional stability

The volumetric swelling coefficient varied among clones for both control and treated wood, depending on soaking time (Fig. 4). Wood hardening treatment significantly improved the dimensional stability of hybrid poplar wood, especially at the start of soaking. The average volumetric swelling coefficient of the controls increased dramatically in

the first 48 hours, with the coefficient remaining nearly constant thereafter. In contrast, the treated samples took much longer (more than 1 week) to reach a relatively steady swelling coefficient, at around 6.8 %, nearly 60 % that of the controls. The average coefficient (11.8 % after 720 hours) obtained for untreated wood was slightly lower than the average volumetric shrinkage of 12.8 % in ten *P. × euramerricana* clones reported by Koubaa et al. [27]. The swelling coefficients of the hardened hybrid poplar samples were comparable to or lower than those of silver maple, red oak, and white ash, for which volumetric shrinkage was around 12.0 %, 16.1 %, and 13.3 % (green to oven-dried), respectively [28]. Control Clone 915303 showed the lowest coefficient after 720 hours at around 10.8 %, more than twice that of treated Clone 915311. Cross-section SEM images of the treated hybrid poplar wood (Fig. 2) clearly show microcracks between the wood cell walls and PMMA. Water that passes through these microcracks into the wood cell therefore caused swelling. Thus, impregnation with MMA does not significantly change the hygroscopic properties of wood as previously reported [21, 29].

Fig.3. FTIR spectra of a) PMMA; treated hybrid poplar wood; and c) untreated hybrid poplar wood.

Another explanation is that water may pass through and fill small pores that the MMA monomer cannot enter. The volume changes during the soaking period were likely due to the absorbed bound water, which contribute to wood swelling. From the combined results of the SEM micrographs, the FTIR spectra, and the dimensional stability analysis, it can be concluded that there should be little or no

interaction between the MMA monomer and the hydroxyl groups of the cellulose fibers.

Fig.4. Average volumetric swelling coefficient (%) for control and treated hybrid poplar clones.

3.4 Surface properties

3.4.1 Janka Hardness

PMMA wood impregnation resulted in substantial increases in Janka hardness for all tested samples. Hardening increased the hardness of virgin wood by 1.5 to 2.9 times. Two of the investigated clones fell into the range of 6.0–6.4 kN, which is comparable to or even better than that of many commercial species used for flooring, such as silver maple and red oak, and even their oil-finished wood [11, 30]. The Janka hardness test is most commonly used to determine whether a species is suitable for applications such as flooring, and it is the industry standard for determining the ability to tolerate denting. Therefore, MMA hardened poplar wood could potentially be used in the wood flooring industry, which would substantially increase the commercial potential of hybrid poplar.

Hardness varied among the studied clones. The highest value was observed for clone 915311. Clone 3531 was in second place. Treatment, clone and their interaction significantly affected the hardness of the studied clones. Relationships between density and hardness were also investigated for several species: northern white cedar, aspen, red oak, white ash, silver maple (Fig. 5). Average hardness showed close relationship with density for the investigated species ($R^2 = 0.89$). The variation in hardness among

species could therefore be explained by variations in wood density.

Fig.5. Relationship between wood density and hardness for different wood species.

Moreover, high impregnation rate increases not only the sample density but also the risk of brittle failure and a decrease in the hardness value. Indeed, the hardening process increased the risks of splitting the sample during the hardness test, although no splits were observed in the control group. The splitting is expected in hardened samples because PMMA hardening renders the samples more brittle [31].

3.4.2 Abrasion resistance

Abrasion resistance is the ability of a material to maintain its surface appearance and structure when subjected to a mechanical action such as rubbing or scratching. Lower wear index values are associated to the better the abrasive resistance. Wear index increased with abrasion cycles, and hardening had a positive effect on wear index (Fig. 6). Wood hardening substantially reduced the wear index of the samples by nearly 50 % after 500 cycles. However, the effect became slightly weaker with increasing abrasion cycles. At 2500 cycles, the effect nearly decreased. This result could be explained by the higher impregnation rate at the wood surface. Moving toward the core, the impregnation rate slightly decreased (Fig. 1), explaining the decrease in abrasion resistance with increasing abrasion cycles.

Wear index varied among clones after 2000 cycles. This implies that hybrid poplars should be appropriately selected for desired surface properties. The hardened wood produced from clones 915311

and 3531 showed the lowest wear indexes at 0.50 and 0.41 after 2000 cycles, respectively. These wear indexes are nonetheless high compared to some commercial flooring species, such as silver maple (0.35) and red oak (0.16) [30], despite the high densities of the above two poplar composites. These relatively high wear indexes may result from surface morphology and roughness, which did not change significantly after MMA treatment. The density of control samples and the hardness of treated wood have played important roles in wear index determination. Koubaa [30] also reported that abrasion resistance was correlated to both surface hardness and material density. Rodriguez et al. [32] found that surface property was related to not only polymer type, but also the additives that chemically bond to the wood substrate. Thus, crosslinking surface structure is liable to improve abrasive resistance, for example, by adding silica nanoparticles. Furthermore, surface coating, which is usually applied over the material, offers an alternative method to reduce friction and obtain better surface properties, allowing more high-value applications.

Fig.6. Variation in abrasion wear index for hardened unhardened wood of hybrid poplar.

3.5 Mechanical properties

3.5.1 Static bending strength

Modulus of elasticity (MOE), proportional limit (PL) and modulus of rupture (MOR) were the most consistently improved properties after hardening treatment (Table 2). This is attributed to the voids in the wood filled by PMMA polymer, which acts as a

bridge effectively transferring the stress from one end of wood cell to the other end. The analysis of variance showed that clone, treatment and their interaction had significant effects on MOE, PL and MOR, except for the interaction on MOE. Treatment significantly and negatively affected strain at MOR for poplar wood. Strains at proportional limit were observed to be increased for the 6 clones, which also indicate good interaction between the PMMA and wood, resulting in improved material elasticity. However, decreases in strain at MOR (S) were found for all studied clones (Table 2). Therefore, wood hardening with MMA weakened the plastic properties of wood and increased the brittleness of the composites. After treatment, clones 3729 showed the best performance in the bending test, followed by clone 915508. Coincidentally, these two clones showed the best properties for corresponding control samples. In contrast, clone 915303 was the worst for both control and treated wood.

3.5.2 Compression strength

After wood hardening with MMA, all properties investigated improved to varying degrees (Table 3). MOE for C_{II} was one of the least enhanced properties, with increases ranging from 2 % to 27 %. The highest increasing rate was observed in clone 915311 at 27 %, followed by clone 915303 at 20 %. On the other hand, the highest MOE values in the composites were in two clones, 915508 and 3729. In contrast, 915508 and 3729 had the highest MOE values of the solid woods. High MOE increasing rates are not consistent with high MOE values after treatment. Highest maximum crushing strength (MCS) parallel to the grain was 42.4 MPa for clone 915508, an increase of 50 % over control, followed by clones 3531 and 3729. These three clones also showed the best performance in the control group. The proportional limit showed a similar trend to ultimate compressive strength. Overall, as for compression parallel to grain, clones 915508, 3531 and 3729 showed the best properties for both control and hardened wood. Most of the gross wood samples for the compression parallel to grain test failed due to collapse caused by the buckling of the relatively thin wood cell walls because of instability of long-column type wood samples. The addition of polymer places a coating on the cell walls, which thickens them and greatly increases their lateral stability.

Table 2 Comparison on static bending tests for the hybrid poplar clones

Treatment	Clone	MOE (GPa)	MOR (MPa)	S (%)
Control	1	4.36 (16) ^a	41.2 (12)	1.86 (18)
	2	4.98 (11)	43.6 (8.3)	1.58 (36)
	3	4.96 (13)	46.5 (8.2)	1.88 (22)
	4	3.77 (8.8)	36.5 (7.4)	1.80 (13)
	5	3.97 (8.2)	34.9 (7.8)	1.71 (33)
	6	3.73 (17)	47.6 (11)	2.47 (16)
Treated	1	4.59 (6.5)	44.7 (3.3)	1.56 (20)
	2	5.37 (11)	52.1 (6.8)	1.58 (33)
	3	5.25 (11)	55.2 (2.4)	1.75 (22)
	4	4.28 (9.1)	42.5 (10)	1.42 (19)
	5	4.68 (3.4)	48.4 (9.9)	1.60 (20)
	6	4.06 (16)	49.6 (5.9)	2.00 (22)

Note: MOE = Modulus of elasticity, MOR = Modulus of Rupture, S = Strain at MOR; ^aCoefficient of variation (%).

Table 3 Comparison on compression tests for the hybrid poplar clones

Treatment	Clone	MOE (GPa)*	MCS (MPa)*	MOE (GPa) ‡
Control	1	2.91 (2.9) ^a	24.1 (8.8)	1.30 (9)
	2	3.57 (16)	28.0 (12)	1.42 (23)
	3	3.66 (12)	28.1 (8.5)	1.79 (18)
	4	2.80 (21)	23.0 (11)	1.36(26)
	5	2.71 (11)	25.1 (3.4)	1.39 (32)
	6	3.22 (15)	26.9 (1.8)	1.78 (16)
Treated	1	3.26 (22)	30.1 (9.2)	1.78 (23)
	2	4.05 (17)	42.4 (8.2)	2.15 (32)
	3	3.72 (11)	32.2 (6.9)	1.96 (15)
	4	3.35 (9.1)	32.6 (7.8)	2.07 (23)
	5	3.43 (14)	34.6 (9.3)	1.93 (32)
	6	3.27 (3.8)	35.0 (10)	2.13 (11)

Note: MOE = Modulus of elasticity, MCS = Maximum crushing strength, *Compression parallel to grain; ‡Compression perpendicular to grain; ^aCoefficient of variation (%).

A wide range of improvements were also observed (10–56 % for MOE and 166–290 % for proportional limit) in compression perpendicular to grain for all studied clones after treatment. These especially high increasing rates are attributable to the polymer

filling the wood. Composites from clones 3531, 915303, 915508 and 3729 showed similar properties, with no significant differences among them. For untreated wood, clones 3729 and 3531 showed the best performance of the 6 clones. In sum, clones 915508 and 3531 obtained the best properties for hardened wood in compression, both parallel and perpendicular to grain. In the solid wood samples, clone 3729 exhibited the best performance.

4 Conclusions

Hardening of hybrid poplar wood through MMA impregnation greatly improved its density, dimensional stability, surface properties and mechanical properties. These improvements were clone-dependent in both untreated wood and MMA-hardened wood. However, the hardening treatment had a negative effect on the wood plastic properties. The hardening mechanism is due to PMMA filling of void spaces in wood structure as demonstrated from SEM images and FTIR analysis. Improved dimensional stability, surface properties, and mechanical properties, make hardened hybrid poplar wood a good alternative to other commercial high-grade species, especially in flooring applications.

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